

Complexation Reaction of Metal Ions with Peptide Systems. Part (V).

The Stability Constants and Thermodynamic Functions of La³⁺, Ce³⁺, Pr³⁺, Nd³⁺ and Sm³⁺ with Glycyl-DL-Valine

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METAL complexes of amino acids and peptides are of theoretical and practical significance. The complexation reactions of number of dipeptides with copper and nickel have been reported in literature¹⁻⁷, but no work appears to have been reported with lanthanums. This paper deals with the study of complexes of La³⁺, Ce³⁺, Pr³⁺, Nd³⁺ and Sm³⁺ with glycyl-DL-valine.

Bjerrum Calvin⁸⁻⁹ pH titration technique as modified by Irving-Rossotti¹⁰ has been employed. Most of peptides are in their zwitter form upto pH 6. One equivalent of OH⁻ is required to titrate the proton from terminal NH₃⁺ group between pH 7 to pH 9. However, in the presence of metal ion the NH₃⁺ is titrated at lower pH because the metal ion competes with H⁺ ion¹¹.

Experimental

The metal nitrates used were of B. D. H. AnalaR quality. The ligand was obtained from Koch-Light Laboratories Ltd., London. All solutions were prepared in doubly distilled carbon dioxide free water. The metal nitrate solutions were standardised by EDTA method. A fresh ligand solution (0.025M) was prepared just before use. Potassium nitrate (1.0M) solution was used to maintain constant ionic strength

of 0.15M. The pH was measured on a photovolt digicord pH meter having a sensitivity of ±0.002. The pH meter was calibrated by suitable buffers. All titrations were carried out in a thermostated bath maintained at temperatures 20 ± 0.1°, 30 ± 0.1° and 40 ± 0.1°. The following sets of solutions were titrated against a standard solution (0.051M) carbonate free potassium hydroxide.

- A) Acid titration : Nitric acid (0.005M, 5ml)
- B) Reagent titration : Nitric acid (0.005M, 5ml)+ reagent (0.025M, 5ml)
- C) Metal titration : Nitric acid (0.005M, 5 ml)+ reagent (0.025M, 5ml)+metal nitrate (0.005M, 5 ml)

In all titrations, the total volume of solution was kept to 50 ml and required amount of potassium nitrate solution (1.0M) was added to bring the ionic background to required level. Nitrogen gas was bubbled through the solution to provide an inert atmosphere. The concentrations were corrected for the changes in volume produced by the addition of alkali during titration.

Results and Discussion

$\bar{n}_H$, $\bar{n}$ and pL were calculated by employing the relationships derived by Irving and Rossotti¹⁰. The practical proton-ligand stability constant (pk₁^H) and the metal-ligand stability constants (log K₁) have been obtained by the Bjerrum half integral method and also graphical methods¹⁰. The results are shown in Table 1.

The values of $\bar{n}$ obtained are of the order of one indicating the formation of 1 : 1 complexes of La³⁺, Ce³⁺, Pr³⁺, Nd³⁺ and Sm³⁺ below the pH range at which precipitation occurred. The data in Table 1 show an increase in the value of logK₁ with increase in temperature.

TABLE 1—PROTONATION CONSTANT OF THE LIGAND, METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE COMPLEXES AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS AT THREE TEMPERATURES

Metal Ions	Protonation constants/metal ligand stability constants	Temperature			$\Delta G(K \text{ cal. mole}^{-1})$			$\Delta H(K \text{ cal. mole}^{-1})$ 30°C	$\Delta S(\text{cal. mole}^{-1} - \text{deg}^{-1})$ 30°C
		20°C	30°C	40°C	20°C	30°C	40°C		
	log pk ₁ ^H	8.47	8.27	8.05					
La ³⁺	log k ₁	3.58	3.60	3.64	4.84	5.01	5.24	1.092	20.1
Ce ³⁺	log k ₁	3.59	3.62	3.66	4.84	5.06	5.27	1.486	21.6
Pr ³⁺	log k ₁	3.59	3.70	3.80	4.84	5.16	5.47	4.433	31.7
Nd ³⁺	log k ₁	3.66	3.76	3.93	4.93	5.24	5.68	5.757	36.3
Sm ³⁺	log k ₁	3.83	3.91	4.02	5.16	5.45	5.79	4.038	31.3

The order of stability constant at 20° has been observed to be $\text{Sm}^{3+} > \text{Nd}^{3+} > \text{Pr}^{3+} \approx \text{Ce}^{3+} \approx \text{La}^{3+}$. A better separation of $\log K_1$ values amongst Pr^{3+} , Ce^{3+} and La^{3+} has been observed at 30° and 40° where it follows the order $\text{Sm}^{3+} > \text{Nd}^{3+} > \text{Pr}^{3+} > \text{Ce}^{3+} > \text{La}^{3+}$.

The values of overall changes in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) have been determined by using the temperature coefficient and Gibbs-Helmholtz equation. These are summarised in Table 1. The value of free energies of formation becomes more negative with increase in temperature. This shows that the complex formation process is spontaneous and the spontaneity increases with increase in temperature. The formation of all the complexes is an endothermic process and it explains the increase in the values of constants with rise in temperature. The complex formation is favoured by the increase in the entropy of the system. It is indicated by the positive values ΔS in all the cases. The low values of formation constants, free energy of formation, and enthalpy changes shows that these metals have less tendency to form complexes with glycyl-DL-valine.

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Rh(III) and Ru(III) Complexes of the Ligand 1-Imino-3-Thioisindoline

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THE ligand 1-Imino-3-Thioisindoline has recently been used for the gravimetric determination of a number of metal ions by the authors¹⁻⁷. The present investigation deals with the Rh(III) and Ru(III) complexes of the ligand. Investigations have indicated that the ligand reacts with these metals at pH ranging from 7.5 to 10.0 giving precipitate of insoluble metal complexes.

All the reagents used were of AnalaR grade. The ligand was prepared by the method of Baguley and Elvidge⁸.

The following stock solutions were prepared.

1. 1-Imino-3-Thioisindoline about 0.1% sodium salt solution of the ligand in NaOH.
2. $\text{RhCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Johnson-Matthey Co.). A 0.25 W/V solution of hydrated salt in water.
3. $\text{RuCl}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, as above.

Preparation of Complexes :

A freshly filtered soln. of the ligand was added in excess to soln. No. 1. A yellow brown ppt. of rhodium complex was obtained. It was digested on a water bath for 10 minutes and then filtered, washed with water for several times and then with alcohol, dried at 70 to 105° in an air oven.

In the case of ruthenium(III) a black ppt. was obtained under similar conditions.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data indicates the metal to ligand ratio as 1:3. Both the complexes were found to be diamagnetic. The infrared spectra of the complexes and the ligand were examined to establish the exact structure of the complexes. The infrared spectra indicates the presence of $\nu(\text{M-N})$ and $\nu(\text{M-S})$ bonds in both the complexes. Coordination of thio-carbonyl sulphur to the metal ion is also clearly indicated; it also indicates the absence of N-H bond in the two complexes. Thus it may easily be concluded that the Rh and Ru ion in the

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